

Effect of necroptosis pathway in pituitary adenoma patients

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Abstract:

Background: Pituitary adenomas imposes burden of morbidity due to hormone hyper secretion and related effects on patients. Molecular mechanism underlying its incidence, development and progression have yet to be elucidated which can provide insights into new and more efficient therapeutic approaches. The involvement of necroptosis as an appealing way of cell death in pathogenesis of pituitary adenomas is perused in the current study.

Methods: The expression level of necroptosis crucial mediators (RIP1K, RIP3K, and MLKL) was assessed via Real-Time PCR in tumor tissues of prevalent functional and nonfunctional pituitary adenoma and normal Pituitary tissues. The effect of Shikonin on the cell viability and induction of apoptosis or necrosis in the presence and absence of necroptosis inhibitor (Necrostatin-1) were evaluated in pituitary adenoma cell line (GH3).

Results: Our results revealed that RIP1K expression level was increased in tumor tissues of different types of pituitary adenomas which was associated with significant decrease in the expression level of RIP3K and MLKL in tumor tissues comparing to normal pituitary. Shikonin reduced the percentage of GH3 viable cells in a dose dependent manner which was associated with the induction of apoptosis and necrosis. The Shikonin-induced cell death was diminished in response to suppression of necroptosis.

Conclusion: Necroptosis pathway is involved in the regulation of pituitary tumor cell proliferation. Suppression of necroptosis resulted in an accelerated cell proliferation which can cause pituitary tumor formation. Therefore, necroptosis biomarkers can be perused as hallmark mediators and the necroptosis pathway activation can be targeted as a therapeutic solution in management of pituitary tumors.

Keywords:

Pituitary adenoma, Necroptosis, Shikonin.

The role of CD44 in cancer progression and it's importance as a potential tumor cell marker

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Abstract:

CD44 is a hyluronan (HA)-binding glycoprotein that is highly expressed in cancers and regulates metastasis via CD44 recruitment to the cell surface. CD44 expression is altered during cellular malfunctioning in the process of tumor progression. CD44 has CD44s standard and CD44v variant forms. These CD44v (v1-v10) variants forms are useful as a diagnostic marker of malignancy and may be consider as a potential target for cancer therapy. CD44, also known as mesenchymal stem cell marker, is actively involved in the maintenance of microenvironemnt of heamtopoetic stem cell (HSC), maintenance of quiescence, apoptosis resistance and homing. Heamtopoetic stem cell (HSC) and Leukemia stem cell (LSC) share many common “stem-cell like” features. LSCs are key factor in disease progression and relapse. As a conventional therapy, TKIs (Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors) are, very effective in the reduction of tumor mass but also show frequent fail to eliminate LSC residing in the secured bone marrow niche. Thus, there is a unmet requirement for combination therapy that targets bulk disease to remove LSC in order to prevent disease progression. In this study, we discussed the promising activity of anti-CD44 monoclonal antibody which blocks the HA-binding domain and initiate the apoptosis process for leukemic cell via mitochondrial pathway.

Keywords:

CD44, Glycoprotein, Anti-CD44, CD44s standard, Cd44v variant, Stem cell marker, Cancer Progression, Metastasis, HA binding domain, HSC Hematopoetic stem cell, LSC Leukemic stem cell, Homing, Apoptosis, Quiescence

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Reversal of hypermethylation and reactivation of glutathione S-transferase pi 1 gene by curcumin in breast cancer cell line

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Abstract:

Background : One of the mechanisms for epigenetic silencing of tumor suppressor genes is hypermethylation of cytosine residue at CpG islands at their promoter region that contributes to malignant progression of tumor. Therefore, activation of tumor suppressor genes that have been silenced by promoter methylation is considered to be very attractive molecular target for cancer therapy. Epigenetic silencing of glutathione S-transferase pi 1, a tumor suppressor gene, is involved in various types of cancers including breast cancer. Epigenetic silencing of tumor suppressor genes can be reversed by several molecules including natural compounds such as polyphenols that can act as a hypomethylating agent. Curcumin has been found to specifically target various tumor suppressor genes and alter their expression. To check the effect of curcumin on the methylation pattern of glutathione S-transferase pi 1 gene in MCF-7 breast cancer cell line in dose-dependent manner.

Material and Methods : To check the reversal of methylation pattern of hypermethylated glutathione S-transferase pi 1, MCF-7 breast cancer cell line was treated with different concentrations of curcumin for different time periods. DNA and proteins of treated and untreated cell lines were isolated, and methylation status of the promoter region of glutathione S-transferase pi 1 was analyzed using methylation-specific polymerase chain reaction assay, and expression of this gene was analyzed by immunoblotting using specific antibodies against glutathione S-transferase pi 1.

Results : A very low and a nontoxic concentration (10 μ M) of curcumin treatment was able to reverse the hypermethylation and led to reactivation of glutathione S-transferase pi 1 protein expression in MCF-7 cells after 72 h of treatment, although the IC₅₀ value of curcumin was found to be at 20 μ M. However, curcumin less than 3 μ M of curcumin could not alter the promoter methylation pattern of glutathione S-transferase pi 1.

Conclusion : Treatment of breast cancer MCF-7 cells with curcumin causes complete reversal of glutathione S-transferase pi 1 promoter hypermethylation and leads to re-expression of glutathione S-transferase pi 1, suggesting it to be an excellent nontoxic hypomethylating agent.

Keywords :

GSTP1; MCF-7; Methylation; breast cancer; curcumin

Celastrol as a pentacyclic triterpenoid with chemopreventive properties

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Abstract:

Celastrol is a highly investigated anticancer moiety. It is a pentacyclic triterpenoid, isolated several decades ago with promising role in chemoprevention. Celastrol has been found to target multiple proinflammatory, angiogenic and metastatic proteins. Inhibition of these targets results in significant reduction of cancer growth, survival and metastasis. This review summarizes the varied molecular targets of celastrol along with insight into the various recently published clinical, preclinical and industrial patents (2011–2017).

Keywords:

- Celastrol: A pentacyclic triterpenoid moiety
- The electrophilic centre within the ring A and ring B as C 2 and C 6
- Anti-metastasis: Inhibition of cancer cell migration from one site to other
- Anti-angiogenesis: Prevention and inhibition of formation of new blood vessel
- Anti-inflammation: Lower down the expression of inflammatory mediator
- Anti-oxidant: Scavenging of free electron carrying species
- Recent filled patents on celastrol and its derivatives with applications

The Efficacy of PARP-Inhibitor in BRCA-Mutated Breast and Ovarian Cancer: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Abstract:

Breast and ovarian cancer are the most common type of cancer in women worldwide. BRCA1 and BRCA2 gene are often mutated in these patients, which is correlated with higher mortality rate. Poly-ADP Ribose Polymerase Inhibitor (PARPi) is a new class of drug targeting the ability to repair DNA damage. These DNA damages are lethal especially in BRCA-mutated cancer cells. It has been used clinically, both as a single agent and in combination with other therapeutic agents. This meta-analysis aimed to assess the efficacy and toxicity of PARPi in BRCA-mutated breast and ovarian cancers. Phase II and III trials comparing PARPi with standard treatment published from 1990 to 2019 were searched using Pubmed, EMBASE, Medline, and Cochrane clinical trials. The primary endpoint was Progression Free Survival (PFS), and the secondary endpoint was drug-related toxicity. Source of heterogeneity was sought using meta-regression. 13 eligible randomized controlled trials were included in the analysis, with 8 ovarian cancer trials and 5 breast cancer trials. PFS in breast cancer were higher compared to control (HR: 0.67; 95%CI: 0.59-0.76) and in ovarian cancer (HR: 0.33; 95%CI: 0.29-0.37), with mean PFS improvement of 3 to 4 months. Type of cancer were found to be the source of heterogeneity in the study. Grade I/II toxicity were higher in PARPi group compared to control for anaemia (OR: 2.64; 95%CI: 1.76-3.95), neutropenia (OR: 1.86; 95%CI: 1.06-3.16), and thrombocytopenia (OR: 3.71; 95%CI: 1.71-8.02). However, Grade III/IV toxicity were similar both in PARPi group compared to control (OR: 1.51; 95%CI: 0.84-2.71). In conclusion, our meta-analysis shows slightly improved PFS and higher grade I/II toxicities in both ovarian and breast cancer patients with BRCA mutation compared to control. We recommend tailoring the use of this drug to each patient's condition, by weighing the risk and benefit of the drug.

Keywords:

PARP-Inhibitor, Breast Cancer, Ovarian Cancer, BRCA, Progression Free Survival, Toxicity

Figure 1. Overall Progression Free Survival for both Breast and Ovarian Cancer.

Since there was a high heterogeneity (I²: 86%) in the study, further meta-regression is required to find out the source of heterogeneity.

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2-NDC from Dithio-carbamates improves ATRA efficacy and oxidative stress induced apoptosis in human acute promyelocytic NB4 cells

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Abstract:

All trans retinoic acid (ATRA) metabolites have been revealed as a potent therapeutic agent for acute promyelocytic leukemia (APL). Dithiocarbamate family is also known as important chemical synthetic compounds in cancer therapy. In the present study, we have evaluated induction of apoptosis in NB4 cells by 2-Nitro-1-Phenylethylpiperidine-1-carbodithioate (2-NDC) from Dithiocarbamate family, and in combination with ATRA. The NB4 cells were cultured and treated in 10-120 μM of the compound for 24-72 hours. The percent of cell viability and growth inhibition were assessed by MTT assay. For evaluation of combinational effect of 2-NDC and ATRA, NB4 cells were treated with 1-2 μM of ATRA and 20 μM of 2-NDC for 24-72 h. 2-NDC inhibited cell growth and viability with IC_{50} of 20 μM . Growth and proliferation of the cells were diminished by more than 85% and cell viability was decreased by about 70% upon 72 h of treatment with 2-NDC and ATRA. We also have assessed apoptosis induction and oxidative stress inducing effect of 2-NDC, ATRA and in combination, on the NB4 cells. We found that 2-NDC triggered apoptosis by expanding intracellular ROS, combined to ATRA. According to results, ATRA (2 μM) raised the amount of ROS production by 10.5% in contrast to control cells, as well as the 2-NDC enhanced it about 8% during 24 h of treatment. Based on these data, we approve that 2-NDC in combination with ATRA can be an efficient candidate for future researches about the treatment of leukemia, especially APL.

Keywords:

Acute Promyelocytic Leukemia, All trans retinoic acid, Apoptosis, Dithio-carbamate, Oxidative Stress.

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Familial Hepatocellular Carcinoma: “A Model For Studying Preventive And Therapeutic Measures”.

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Abstract:

Introduction : Hepatocellular Cancer (Hcc) Is The Fifth Most Common Cancer Worldwide With More Than 80% Of Case Found In Endemic Areas Of Hepatitis B Such As Africa Or East Asia. A Family History Of Liver Cancer Increases Hcc Risk, Independently Of Hepatitis. Only Limited Attention Has Been Given To The Role Of Primary Genetic Factors In Hcc.

Objective : The Aim Of The Study Was To Identify Case Studies On Familial Hcc, The Primary Genetic And Epigenetic Factors, And The Clues It Renders To Prevention And Therapy.

Materials & Methods : Electronic Searches Of The Medline (Pubmed) Database Was Performed To Identify Original Published Case Studies On Familial Hcc.

Results : Fifteen Cases Of Familial Hcc Were Reported Between 1965- 2016. Familial Clusters Of Hbv/C Serum Markers Was Associated With An Over 70-Fold Elevated Hcc Risk, Poor Prognosis And An Earlier Age Of Onset. A Multifactorial Inheritance Including Novel Dicer 1 Germline Mutation And Altered Liver Zonation Contributed To The Risk. Global Gene Expression Profiling Revealed A Small Set Of Genes, Spink 1, A Secretory Trypsin Inhibitor As A Potential Hcc Marker. An Over Expression Of The Apolipoprotein Family And Serum Amyloid A Were Reported. Epigenetic Variation Studies On Monozygotic Twins With Familial Hcc Identified The Susceptibility Loci Sensitive To Modification By The Environment.

Discussion & Conclusions :

The Hepatitis B Virus Is Directly Oncogenic, And By Incorporating Into Host Genetic Material Can Cause Hcc In The Absence Of Cirrhosis. The Highest Risk Of Hcc May Occur In Families In Which A Hereditary Component Is Acting In Concert With Hepatitis B Virus. Hepatitis Vaccination Should Be Given The Highest Priority, And Screening Of First Degree Relatives To Detect Early, Asymptomatic Disease Is Mandatory.

Keywords :

Familial, Hepatocellular, Carcinoma